

ONLINE APPENDIX

**Price Pass-Through of Austria's
Single-Use Plastics Producer Charges:
Evidence from Retail Offer Spells**

Initial Appendix

Felix Reichel

This appendix accompanies the main paper. It documents sample construction, variable definitions, descriptive statistics, regression tables, and all supplementary figures.

CONTENTS

APPENDIX A SAMPLE CONSTRUCTION AND COUNTERFACTUAL DESIGN

- A.1 Construction of the Treated Sample
- A.2 Intended Counterfactual Design
- A.3 Implemented Counterfactual Sample
- A.4 Implemented Counterfactual Filter and Baseline-Survivor Restriction
- A.5 Implications for Panel Composition and Identification
- A.6 Summary of Interpretation

APPENDIX B DATA DICTIONARY

- B.1 Notes on Variable Encoding
- B.2 Core Variables Used in the Empirical Analysis

APPENDIX C TABLES

- C.1 Descriptive Statistics of Non-Aggregated Original Offer Spells
- C.2 Regression Results

APPENDIX D FIGURES

- D.1 Histograms and Descriptive Figures for the Original Non-Aggregated Offer-Spell Data
- D.2 Correlation Among Energy Control Variables
- D.3 Per-Category Parallel-Trend Diagnostics

D.4 Regression Coefficient Plots for the Original Non-Aggregated Offer-Spell Data

D.5 Regression Coefficient Plots for Aggregated Duration-Weighted Offer-Spells on the Balloons Subsample

D.6 Energy Input-Price Series: Full Sample and Event Window

APPENDIX E ALTERNATIVE DURATION-WEIGHTED MONTHLY PANEL

E.1 Data Dictionary

E.2 Pipeline: Step-by-Step Construction

E.3 Sample Construction in Detail

E.4 Figures

Appendix A: Sample Construction and Counterfactual Design

This appendix documents the construction of the treated and counterfactual samples from the underlying retail offer-spell data and clarifies the gap between the counterfactual design initially envisaged and the control group ultimately implemented in the estimation code. Because the credibility of the empirical design turns in part on the comparability of treated and untreated observations, these sample-construction choices warrant explicit documentation.

The raw data comprise offer-level observations spanning 2020:01–2024:12. Let s index offer spells, where each spell corresponds to a product–retailer listing observed over a finite interval defined by start and end timestamps. Two raw input files underlie the analysis sample: *plastics_regulation_obs.csv*, which contains the treated-side observations, and *plastics_regulation_counterfactual_obs.csv*, which contains the counterfactual observations. Appendix B provides a variable-level description of these files.

A.1 Construction of the treated sample

The treated sample is defined through keyword matches in product titles, recorded in the raw variable *produkt_bez*. Matching is implemented through case-insensitive string patterns designed to identify product groups plausibly exposed to the Austrian SUP-related regulatory regime. Let $M_i^T \in \{0, 1\}$ denote an indicator equal to one if product i matches at least one treated keyword pattern and zero otherwise. A product is assigned to the treated sample whenever $M_i^T = 1$, subject to the subsequent cleaning, deduplication, and panel-construction steps of the empirical pipeline.

Substantively, the aim is to capture product classes that either fall directly within the regulatory scope or are sufficiently close to the affected domain that their prices may respond to the altered compliance environment. Table 2 reports the keyword categories used to construct the treated sample. The first column gives the internal category label used in the data pipeline, the second provides a natural English translation, and the third lists the underlying keyword patterns. These categories should be read as operational search rules rather than as a legal classification in the strict statutory sense. They convert a regulatory concept into an empirically workable sample definition within the constraints of title-based retail data.

Table 2: Keyword categories used to construct the treated sample

Internal category	cate- Translation	Keyword patterns
tabak	Tobacco-related products and filters	tabakfilter; zigarettenfilter; zigarette; rauchwaren; nikotinprodukt; tabakprodukt; e-zigarette; rauchgerät; tabakröhre; filterzigarette
becher	Single-use cups and to-go drink cups	to-go becher; einwegbecher; kaffeebecher; kunststoffbecher; trinkbecher; coffee to go; takeaway becher; getränkebecher; wegwerfbecher; plastikbecher
lebensmittelbehälter	Single-use food containers	lebensmittelbehälter; takeaway box; to-go behälter; einwegbox; essensbox; menüschale; mittagsschale; essensbehälter; food container; kunststoffschale
tueten_folien	Plastic wraps, films, and small packaging	folienverpackung; verpackungsfolie; plastikfolie; säckchen; tütchen; verpackungseinheit; folie verpackung; beutelverpackung; kunststoffverpackung; kleinverpackung
flaschen_ohne_pfand	Non-deposit beverage bottles, especially disposable plastic bottles	getränkeflasche; pet flasche; einwegflasche; kunststoffflasche; saftflasche; wasserflasche; getränkebehälter; softdrinkflasche; limonadenflasche; to-go flasche
flaschen_mit_pfand	Deposit and reusable beverage bottles	mehrwegflasche; pfandflasche; getränkeflasche pfand; getränkebehälter pfand; rückgabeflasche; flasche mit pfand; getränkeflasche mehrweg
plastiktueten	Plastic carrier bags and shopping bags	kunststofftragetasche; plastiktüte; einkaufstüte; leichte tragetasche; dünne plastiktüte; tragetasche einweg; einwegtragetasche; tüte plastik; kleine plastiktasche

Continued on next page

Internal category	Translation	Keyword patterns
feuchttuecher	Wet wipes and disposable cleaning or hygiene wipes	feuchttuch; reinigungstuch; hygienetuch; babyfeuchttuch; pflegetuch; intimtuch; kosmetiktuch; einwegtuch; nassreinigungstuch; desinfektionstuch
luftballons	Balloons and balloon decoration products	luftballon; ballon latex; partyballon; heliumballon; einwegballon; deko ballon; ballonset; kinderballon; ballon dekoration

Products matching one or more of these patterns are assigned to the treated sample. The treated sample is therefore title-defined. Its coverage consequently depends on the informativeness and consistency of product naming conventions in the marketplace data.

A.2 Intended counterfactual design

The original counterfactual design was meant to select products similar in retail context and use environment, yet not directly exposed to the SUP regime. Let $M_i^{C,0} \in \{0,1\}$ denote an indicator for membership in this originally intended counterfactual design. The guiding idea was to construct a comparison group from reusable, natural-material, refillable, or otherwise non-regulated alternatives to the treated product groups. Such a design would have produced a conceptually closer control group by comparing treated products with adjacent goods that occupy similar retail environments while plausibly remaining outside the direct scope of the regulation.

Table 3 lists these intended counterfactual categories. As with the treated keywords, the first column gives the internal design label, the second provides a natural English translation, and the third reports the underlying keyword patterns. These categories are best understood as an empirical approximation to a conceptual design rather than as the final implemented sample rule.

Table 3: Initial keyword categories for the counterfactual sample

Internal category	Translation	Keyword patterns
Tabakprodukte – rare substitutes	Tobacco alternatives and non-standard smoking substitutes	%kräuterzigarett%; %pfeife%; %zigarre%; %snus%; %verdampfer ohne nikotin%; %rauchfreies nikotin%
To-go cups – reusable or natural materials	Reusable or natural-material drink cups	%keramikbecher%; %emaillebecher%; %kupferbecher%; %kokosnussbecher%; %mehrweg goblet%; %glas tumbler%
Food containers – non-plastic materials	Food containers made of glass, ceramic, wood, or similar materials	%tiffin box%; %glasdose%; %keramikbehälter%; %holzbox%; %wachstuchbox%
Bags and wraps – natural or biodegradable materials	Natural-material bags, wraps, and biodegradable packaging	%wachstuch%; %stoffverpackung%; %jutesäckchen%; %leinenbeutel%; %reis-papierverpackung%
Bottles without deposit – alternative materials	Non-deposit bottles made from alternative materials	%glasflasche klein%; %keramikflasche%; %steinzeugflasche%; %kupferflasche%; %emailleflasche%; %bambusflasche%
Bottles with deposit – reusable alternatives	Reusable and refillable bottle alternatives	%milchflasche glas%; %bierflasche glas%; %nachfüllflasche%; %tee flasche glas%; %flasche aus holz%
Carrier bags – textile-based alternatives	Textile and reusable carrier bags	%baumwolltasche handgefertigt%; %jutebeutel bio%; %papiertüte deluxe%; %leinentasche%; %upcycling tasche%; %netztasche%
Wet-wipe alternatives – textile products	Reusable cloth-based wipe alternatives	%baumwolltuch%; %waschlappen bio%; %leinen tuch%; %textiltuch%; %nachhaltiges pfegetuch%
Balloon substitutes – decorative alternatives	Non-balloon decorative substitutes	%stoffgirlande%; %papierrosette%; %wimpelkette%; %papierlaterne%; %naturdeko%; %holzdeko%; %stoffblume%

Had this broader design been implemented in full, the counterfactual sample would have resembled a material- and use-case-adjacent comparison group. In that sense, the intended design was conceptually stronger than a generic untreated control because it sought to hold fixed at least part of the retail environment in which treated products were sold.

A.3 Implemented counterfactual sample

In the final implementation, however, the counterfactual product list was not the broader set of adjacent alternatives summarized in Table 3. Instead, the implemented control sample was narrowed to a single keyword, *grafikkarte*, whose natural translation is *graphics card*. Let $M_i^C \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the implemented counterfactual-match indicator. In the final code, $M_i^C = 1$ if and only if the product title matches this keyword rule and satisfies the additional life-cycle restrictions discussed below.

The implemented counterfactual sample is therefore not a broad taxonomy-matched control group based on reusable or non-regulated substitutes. Rather, it is a selected untreated sample defined by one specific product keyword. This narrowing matters for the economic interpretation of the estimated treatment effects because the untreated comparison group is now drawn from a more specialized product domain that is unlikely to reproduce the full retail context of the treated goods.

A.4 Implemented counterfactual filter and baseline-survivor restriction

The control sample is further restricted by an explicit baseline-survivor filter. Let b_i denote the product birth timestamp and d_i the product death timestamp. Let t_0^{base} denote the baseline timestamp corresponding to 2020-01-01 00:00:00 UTC; in the data pipeline, $t_0^{base} = 1577836800$. The implemented counterfactual sample can then be written as $\mathcal{C} = \{i : M_i^C = 1, b_i \leq t_0^{base}, (d_i = \emptyset \text{ or } d_i > t_0^{base})\}$.

Operationally, this means that the implemented control sample is restricted to products that were already alive at the start of the sample period. All products entering after 2020:01 are excluded from the control group by construction, as are products that had already disappeared before the initial sample month.

A.5 Implications for panel composition and identification

The baseline-survivor restriction has direct implications for panel composition and, in turn, for the interpretation of the identifying comparison. Because the control sample is conditioned on being alive at the beginning of the sample window, it mechanically overrepresents older,

more persistent, and potentially more established products. Conversely, it underrepresents short-lived products, later entrants, and products with more intermittent market presence.

Formally, the observed control sample is not drawn from the full untreated population \mathcal{U} , but from the selected subset $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{U}$ satisfying the survival condition at t_0^{base} . This matters for at least three reasons. First, the retained panel is tilted toward incumbent or long-lived products. Second, if turnover patterns differ systematically between treated and untreated goods, the restriction may induce differential sample selection unrelated to the regulation itself. Third, the final empirical panel no longer represents the full evolving market over 2020:01–2024:12, but instead a selected survivor cohort defined at baseline.

The selection issue is therefore not one of random attrition. Rather, it is a form of systematic conditioning on survival at the start of the sample. If survival is correlated with price levels, retailer persistence, assortment quality, shipping conditions, or product type, treatment–control comparability may be affected. This does not invalidate the empirical design, but it does narrow the estimand: the resulting treatment effect should be interpreted relative to a specific untreated survivor cohort rather than relative to the full market of potentially available untreated goods.

A.6 Summary of interpretation

Four features of the sample-construction process are central for interpretation. First, the treated sample is defined through keyword matches in product titles. Second, the intended counterfactual design originally relied on adjacent but plausibly non-regulated product alternatives. Third, the implemented counterfactual design was narrowed to the single keyword *grafikkarte* (graphics card). Fourth, the implemented control sample excludes post-2020 entrants through a baseline-survivor restriction.

Taken together, these choices imply that the control group should not be interpreted as a broad taxonomy-matched market comparison. Instead, it is a selected counterfactual sample defined by a specific keyword and conditioned on survival at the start of the observation window. The empirical estimates should be interpreted against that design choice throughout the paper.

Appendix B: Data Dictionary

This appendix documents the variables contained in the raw retail offer-spell files used to construct the treated and counterfactual samples described in Appendix A. The underlying files are *plastics_regulation_obs.csv* and *plastics_regulation_counterfactual_obs.csv*. Both contain retail offer spells observed over 2020:01–2025. The unit of observation is an individual retail offer spell, that is, a listing for a product at a particular retailer that remains active over an interval defined by start and end timestamps.

Table 4 provides a variable-level overview of the fields observed in the raw files. To improve readability, the first column reports the raw variable name, while the remaining columns provide a substantive interpretation in standard prose. Whenever the meaning of a field cannot be established with certainty from the raw extract alone, this is stated explicitly.

Table 4: Variable-level data dictionary for the retail offer-spell files

Raw variable	Type	Description	Notes / example
angebot_id	integer	Unique identifier for the offer-spell observation.	Offer-level primary key.
produkt_id	integer	Product identifier.	Links multiple offers to the same product.
haendler_bez	string	Retailer or seller name/identifier associated with the offer.	Example: amazon-de.
preis_min	numeric	Minimum observed price during the offer spell.	Measured in observed currency units.
preis_avg	numeric	Average observed price during the offer spell.	In some rows equal to preis_min and preis_max.
preis_max	numeric	Maximum observed price during the offer spell.	Captures within-spell price variation.
avail	integer	Availability status code.	Appears numerically coded; exact coding not directly observed.
oe_vk	numeric / indicator	Austria-specific shipping or sales condition variable (inferred).	Exact semantics uncertain.
oe_nn	numeric / indicator	Austria-specific condition variable (inferred).	Exact semantics uncertain.
de_vk	numeric / indicator	Germany-specific shipping or sales condition variable (inferred).	Exact semantics uncertain.
de_nn	numeric / indicator	Germany-specific condition variable (inferred).	Exact semantics uncertain.

Continued on next page

Raw variable	Type	Description	Notes / example
oe_kr	numeric	Austria-specific cost measure, plausibly shipping cost (inferred).	Missing in some rows.
de_kr	numeric	Germany-specific cost measure, plausibly shipping cost (inferred).	Example values include 3.99.
anz_angebote	integer	Number of offers associated with the product or spell.	Likely contemporaneous offer count.
dtimebegin	integer (Unix time)	Start timestamp of the offer spell.	Unix epoch seconds.
dtimeend	integer (Unix time)	End timestamp of the offer spell.	Unix epoch seconds.
produkt_id_1	integer	Duplicate or joined product identifier.	Matches produkt_id in example rows.
dtime_birth	integer (Unix time)	Product birth or first-seen timestamp.	Product-level life-cycle marker.
dtime_death	integer (Unix time)	Product death or last-seen timestamp.	Product-level life-cycle marker.
produkt_bez	string	Product title or product description.	Used in keyword-based sample assignment.
subsubkat	string	Fine product category.	Examples include spzgif and blufscifi.
week	integer / string	Calendar week identifier.	Example: 202045.
clicks_ijt	numeric	Clicks associated with the product–retailer–time cell (inferred).	Naming suggests item i , retailer j , and time t .
haendler_bez_1	string	Duplicate or joined retailer identifier.	Mirrors haendler_bez in example rows.

Continued on next page

x

Raw variable	Type	Description	Notes / example
is_at	binary	Indicator that the retailer is associated with Austria.	Equals 1 for Austria-specific sellers.
is_de	binary	Indicator that the retailer is associated with Germany.	Equals 1 for Germany-specific sellers.
is_uk	binary	Indicator that the retailer is associated with the United Kingdom.	Equals 1 for UK-specific sellers.
is_nl	binary	Indicator that the retailer is associated with the Netherlands.	Equals 1 for Netherlands-specific sellers.
laden	binary	Indicator for in-store purchase option (inferred).	The German term suggests a physical-store channel.
abhol	binary	Indicator for pick-up or click-and-collect option.	Often empty in example rows.
online	binary	Indicator for online purchase availability.	Frequently equals 1 in observed sample rows.
lon	numeric	Longitude coordinate associated with retailer location.	Example around 11.59.
lat	numeric	Latitude coordinate associated with retailer location.	Example around 48.18.
versandk.default	string / numeric	Default shipping-cost field.	Mixed content possible.
kunden_id	integer	Customer or seller account identifier (inferred).	Appears retailer-account specific.
mastercard	binary	Indicator that Mastercard is accepted.	Equals 1 if accepted.
visa	binary	Indicator that Visa is accepted.	Equals 1 if accepted.
amex	binary	Indicator that American Express is accepted.	Equals 1 if accepted.
dinersclub	binary	Indicator that Diners Club is accepted.	Often missing or zero.
vk_at	binary	Indicator for Austrian <i>vk</i> condition (inferred).	Exact interpretation uncertain.

Continued on next page

Raw variable	Type	Description	Notes / example
vk_de	binary	Indicator for German <i>vk</i> condition (inferred).	Exact interpretation uncertain.
nn_at	binary	Indicator for Austrian <i>nn</i> condition (inferred).	Exact interpretation uncertain.
nn_de	binary	Indicator for German <i>nn</i> condition (inferred).	Exact interpretation uncertain.
liefert_at	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to Austria.	Equals 1 if delivery to Austria is offered.
liefert_de	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to Germany.	Equals 1 if delivery to Germany is offered.
liefert_uk	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to the United Kingdom.	Equals 1 if delivery to the United Kingdom is offered.
liefert_pl	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to Poland.	Equals 1 if delivery to Poland is offered.
liefert_nl	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to the Netherlands.	Equals 1 if delivery to the Netherlands is offered.
liefert_ie	binary	Indicator that the seller delivers to Ireland.	Equals 1 if delivery to Ireland is offered.
is_pl	binary	Indicator that the retailer is associated with Poland.	Equals 1 for Poland-specific sellers.
dtimebegin_1	integer (Unix time)	(Unix Duplicate or joined start timestamp.	Exact level inferred.
dtimeend_1	integer (Unix time)	(Unix Duplicate or joined end timestamp.	Exact level inferred.
row_num	integer	Row sequence number within grouped data or deduplication procedure.	Equals 1 in the sample excerpt.

B.1 Notes on variable encoding

Several coding details warrant explicit mention. First, timestamp variables such as *dtimebegin*, *dtimeend*, *dtime_birth*, and *dtime_death* appear to be stored as Unix epoch time in seconds. Second, variables prefixed by country codes, including *oe_*, *de_*, *is_*, and *liefert_*, appear to encode market-specific conditions, seller origin, or delivery availability. Third, several fields appear to have been duplicated during joins or merge operations, including *produkt_id_1*, *haendler_bez_1*, *dtimebegin_1*, and *dtimeend_1*. Finally, some abbreviations—especially *vk*, *nn*, and *kr*—cannot be identified with full certainty from the raw extract alone; these variables are therefore marked as inferred in Table 4.

B.2 Core variables used in the empirical analysis

The empirical analysis relies primarily on five groups of raw variables. The first comprises identifiers, in particular *angebot_id*, *produkt_id*, and *haendler_bez*. The second consists of timing variables, notably *dtimebegin*, *dtimeend*, and *week*. The third includes the core price measures *preis_min*, *preis_avg*, and *preis_max*. The fourth comprises sample-assignment variables such as *produkt_bez* and *subsubkat*. The fifth contains market-coverage and seller-characteristic variables, including *is_at*, *is_de*, *is_uk*, *is_nl*, *is_pl*, and the delivery indicators *liefert_ℓ*. Together, these variables are sufficient to reconstruct panel timing, define treated and control observations, and derive the main price and availability outcomes used in the paper.

Appendix C: Tables

C.1 Descriptive statistics of non-aggregated original offer spells

This subsection reports auxiliary summary statistics for the estimation sample, the composition of the treated product universe, and the time variation in the monthly energy-input controls. The tables are included here so that the appendix remains self-contained.

The treated offer-spell panel is larger than the control panel both in observations and in active units. The treated sample contains 1,738,870 spell-month observations from 20,721 units, while the control sample contains 1,039,833 observations from 7,054 units. In levels, mean monthly prices are similar across groups, although the treated sample exhibits substantially greater dispersion. Median prices are somewhat higher among treated listings than among controls, and the treated sample also shows a modestly higher mean log price in both the full sample and the main policy subperiods considered here.

Table A1: Descriptive statistics: offer-spell panel by treatment status

	Treated (SUP products)			Control (non-SUP products)		
	Full	Pre-policy	Post-payment	Full	Pre-policy	Post-payment
Obs.	1,738,870	870,500	468,450	1,039,833	690,900	163,051
Units	20,721	—	—	7,054	—	—
<i>Average monthly price (EUR)</i>						
Mean	24.99	23.95	26.86	24.38	24.65	24.71
SD	373.42	526.32	38.49	70.75	83.67	23.92
Median	18.95	18.09	19.29	15.64	14.99	16.95
p10	8.90	9.36	8.51	6.13	5.96	7.05
p90	38.19	36.38	40.94	53.90	53.90	59.47
<i>Log average monthly price</i>						
Mean	2.94	2.92	2.97	2.81	2.79	2.89
SD	0.61	0.54	0.70	0.80	0.82	0.76

Notes: Post-payment refers to months from March 2024 onward. Price statistics are computed on spell-level average prices.

Within the treated sample, exposure is concentrated in a few categories, especially To-go cups, which account for 15,933 units and 1,312,574 observations. Balloons, Tobacco filters, Wet wipes, and Plastic wrap also contribute meaningful shares of the treated sample, while categories such as Plastic bags and Deposit bottles remain very small. Price levels vary markedly across categories, with the lowest means observed for Wet wipes and Plastic wrap and the highest means observed for Tobacco filters and Plastic bags. This heterogeneity is informative for both the composition and the scope of treated products.

The monthly energy controls also vary substantially across policy phases. Brent crude prices are highest on average during the reporting-only period, while the German energy im-

Table A2: Treated sample composition by keyword category

Category	SUP fee (€/t)	Units	Obs.	Mean price	Mean $\ln(p)$	SD $\ln(p)$
Tobacco filters	450	935	83,394	67.94	3.291	0.866
Balloons	450	2,078	110,254	29.60	3.159	0.735
Plastic bags	225	11	1,168	232.35	5.434	0.171
Food containers	225	319	39,027	37.74	3.609	0.212
Dep. bottles	225	29	11,372	27.62	3.303	0.175
To-go cups	225	15,933	1,312,574	22.83	2.944	0.542
Non-dep. bottles	225	127	20,480	21.75	2.763	0.907
Plastic wrap	225	562	57,559	14.14	2.458	0.614
Wet wipes	225	727	103,042	12.02	2.370	0.413
Control (non-SUP spells)	—	7,054	1,039,833	24.38	2.81	0.80

Notes: Categories are ordered by expected SUP exposure, first by fee tier and then by mean log price. Control denotes non-SUP spell baseline-survivor listings.

port index is elevated both before the policy and during the reporting-only phase. Austrian gas prices are most volatile in the pre-policy period, with a standard deviation of 60.05 and a maximum above EUR 215/MWh, before becoming lower and more stable in later phases. These patterns are consistent with a shifting common cost environment over the sample horizon.

Table A3: Descriptive statistics: monthly energy input-price controls by policy phase

Series	Phase	N	Mean	SD	Min	p25	Median	p75	Max
Brent crude (USD/bbl)	Pre-policy	38	71.68	26.17	18.38	51.19	73.66	88.95	122.71
	Reporting-only	12	82.34	5.80	74.84	78.23	81.53	85.02	93.72
	Payment-due	22	74.18	7.72	62.54	68.02	73.94	80.09	89.94
DE energy import index	Pre-policy	38	121.33	67.75	37.20	61.50	99.45	177.83	260.00
	Reporting-only	12	122.33	7.71	113.90	115.80	120.05	129.15	134.50
	Payment-due	22	110.11	9.47	96.40	100.47	113.90	116.90	125.20
AT gas (EUR/MWh)	Pre-policy	38	61.99	60.05	5.93	13.33	31.38	100.50	215.93
	Reporting-only	12	39.91	7.46	30.86	35.09	36.76	45.54	55.25
	Payment-due	22	37.86	6.55	27.16	34.09	37.56	40.82	53.27

Notes: Monthly observations run from January 2020 through December 2025. Pre-policy denotes months before March 2023. Reporting-only covers March 2023 through February 2024. Payment-due begins in March 2024.

Taken together, these descriptive statistics indicate that treated and control samples are broadly comparable in price levels, while the treated universe remains highly heterogeneous in category composition and product pricing. At the same time, the background energy-cost environment changes materially across policy phases, which supports the inclusion of common time-varying controls in the empirical analysis.

C.2 Regression results

The tables in this subsection collect regression results that complement, extend, or further disaggregate the main specifications discussed in the empirical-results chapter. The objective is to archive all tables required for replication and interpretation, even where not all of them warrant detailed discussion in the main text.

Table A4: Three-by-two two-way fixed-effects estimates of SUP treatment effects on monthly prices

	Dependent variable: $\ln(\text{Average Monthly Price})$	
	(1) Three-by-two TWFE Clustered by unit	(2) Three-by-two TWFE Clustered by retailer
Treated $\times \mathbf{1}\{\text{Legal-to-payment period}\}$	0.1377*** (0.0240)	0.1377 (0.0945)
Treated $\times \mathbf{1}\{\text{Post-payment period}\}$	0.0450 (0.0291)	0.0450 (0.0756)
Unit fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Month fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Standard errors	Unit	Retailer
Observations	51,537	51,537
R^2	0.9197	0.9197
Within R^2	0.0075	0.0075

Notes: The table reports three-by-two two-way fixed-effects estimates of the association between SUP treatment status and monthly log average prices. The omitted category is the pre-legal period, so both coefficients are interpreted relative to that baseline. Column (1) reports standard errors clustered at the unit level, while column (2) reports standard errors clustered at the retailer level. All specifications include unit and month fixed effects. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. Significance levels are denoted by *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.10$.

Table A5: Alternative TWFE estimates of SUP treatment effects on monthly prices

	Dependent variable: $\ln(\text{Average Monthly Price})$	
	(1) Standard TWFE	(2) Three-by-two TWFE
Treated \times Post-payment	0.0398*** (0.0044)	
Treated \times 1{Report-only period}		0.0782*** (0.0082)
Treated \times 1{Payment-due period}		0.0548*** (0.0052)
Unit fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Month fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Standard errors	Clustered by unit	Clustered by unit
Observations	103,074	103,074
Number of units	3,213	3,213
R^2	0.9088	0.9097
Within R^2	0.0023	0.0120
RMSE	0.2382	0.2370

Notes: The table reports alternative two-way fixed-effects estimates of treatment effects on monthly log average prices. Column (1) presents a standard TWFE specification with a single post-payment interaction. Column (2) presents a three-by-two specification that distinguishes between a report-only phase and a payment-due phase. All specifications include unit and month fixed effects. Standard errors are reported in parentheses and clustered at the unit level. Significance levels are denoted by *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.10$.

Table A6: Event-study estimates of Austrian balloon prices around the first payment date

Event time	ln(Average Price _{it})		Event time	ln(Average Price _{it})	
	Coefficient	Standard error		Coefficient	Standard error
Payment month ($t = 0$, 2024:03)	0.446***	(0.060)	$t + 6$ (2024:09)	0.309*	(0.148)
		(+55.9%)			(+34.7%)
$t + 1$ (2024:04)	0.442***	(0.108)	$t + 7$ (2024:10)	0.207**	(0.093)
		(+54.8%)			(+22.5%)
$t + 2$ (2024:05)	0.433***	(0.112)	$t + 8$ (2024:11)	0.187**	(0.067)
		(+53.2%)			(+20.3%)
$t + 3$ (2024:06)	0.516***	(0.133)	$t + 9$ (2024:12)	0.043	(0.075)
		(+66.2%)			(+4.1%)
$t + 4$ (2024:07)	0.311***	(0.081)			
		(+36.0%)			
$t + 5$ (2024:08)	0.248***	(0.079)			
		(+27.8%)			
Observations	178		Products included	15	
Product fixed effects	Yes		Sample window	2020:01–2024:12	
Month fixed effects	Yes		Treatment month	2024:03	
Adjusted R^2	0.964		Final sample month	2024:12	
RMSE	0.118		Standard errors	Clustered by product	

Notes: The table reports event-study estimates of Austrian balloon prices around the first payment date, March 2024, which defines event time $t = 0$. The estimation sample covers monthly observations from 2020:01 through 2024:12. Because the sample ends in 2024:12, the latest observable post-treatment horizon is $t + 9$. All specifications include product and month fixed effects. Standard errors clustered at the product level are reported in parentheses. Bold values in parentheses report Kennedy-corrected percentage effects for the semilog specification, calculated as

$$100 \times \left[\exp \left(\hat{\beta} - \frac{1}{2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\beta}) \right) - 1 \right],$$

where $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\beta}) = \widehat{\text{SE}}(\hat{\beta})^2$. The omitted category is the pre-payment reference period. Significance levels are denoted by *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, and * $p < 0.10$.

Appendix D: Figures

D.1 Histograms and descriptive figures for the original non-aggregated offer-spell data

This subsection reports additional descriptive figures based on the original, non-aggregated offer-spell data. The purpose is fourfold: to document the composition of the treated sample, to compare the cross-sectional distributions of prices and spell durations between treated and control observations, to show how observation counts evolve over time, and to illustrate category-specific relative price movements over the sample period. These figures are informative about the raw data structure prior to aggregation and help motivate the heterogeneity addressed in the empirical design.

Figure D1 reports the composition of the treated sample by keyword category, measured in distinct retailer–product units. The treated sample is dominated by To-go cups, which account for by far the largest category, followed at a considerable distance by Balloons and Tobacco filters. All remaining categories represent comparatively small shares of treated units. The labels also report the applicable SUP fee tier, showing that both the EUR 225/t and EUR 450/t groups are represented, although most treated exposure is concentrated in EUR 225/t To-go cups.

Figure D1: Treated sample composition by keyword category in the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. Bar lengths report the number of distinct treated retailer–product units, and labels indicate the applicable SUP fee tier.

Figure D2 compares the log-price distribution of treated and control observations and then disaggregates the treated distribution by product category. In the pooled comparison, the two

groups overlap substantially, but the treated distribution is shifted modestly to the right, indicating somewhat higher typical prices. At the same time, the category-specific densities reveal marked heterogeneity within the treated sample. Some categories are tightly concentrated over narrow price ranges, whereas others display broader support or distinct modal values. This variation makes clear that treatment status captures a diverse set of products rather than a single homogeneous product group.

Figure D2: Log-price distributions in the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. The left panel compares treated and control observations. The right panel reports the treated log-price distribution separately by keyword category.

Figure D3 reports two additional features of the raw panel. The left panel shows the distribution of observed spell lengths, measured in months per unit. Both treated and control units are concentrated at relatively short durations, but each group also exhibits a long right tail of more persistent listings. The right panel plots monthly observation counts for treated and control units. Treated observations rise markedly over time, especially after 2023, whereas the control series remains lower and more stable. The figure also shows that the treated sample expands around the policy window, which is relevant for interpreting both composition changes and the precision of period-specific estimates.

Finally, Figure D4 illustrates heterogeneous relative price paths by category in event time using the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. Each series is normalized to its value at $t = -1$, and the control series is included for comparison. Several treated categories remain close to zero around the policy dates, while others display pronounced deviations, especially in the post-payment period. The figure therefore highlights substantial cross-category heterogeneity in raw price dynamics, reinforcing the view that treatment effects may differ materially across product classes even before a more structured regression framework is imposed.

Taken together, these figures show that the original offer-spell data combine substantial

Figure D3: Spell-length and observation-count patterns in the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. The left panel shows the distribution of observed months per unit. The right panel plots monthly unit-month observation counts for treated and control groups, with policy-phase markers indicated by the vertical lines and shaded regions.

Figure D4: Category-level relative log-price paths in the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. Each series is normalized to its value at $t = -1$, and the vertical lines mark the reporting and payment policy thresholds.

cross-sectional heterogeneity with nontrivial time variation in sample composition and relative prices. The treated sample is heavily concentrated in a few categories, price distributions differ across both treatment status and product type, spell durations are strongly skewed, and raw category-level price paths evolve differently around the policy thresholds. These descriptive patterns provide useful background for the aggregated specifications reported in the main text.

D.2 Correlation among energy control variables

Figure D5 reports the pairwise correlations among the three energy control variables used in the analysis.

Figure D5: Pairwise correlations among Brent crude prices, the German energy import index, and Austrian gas prices.

D.3 Per-category parallel-trend diagnostics

Figure D6 reports a visual parallel-trends diagnostic separately for each treated keyword category, comparing the treated series with its matched control counterpart in event time relative to payment onset in March 2024. In each panel, the price index is normalized to 100 at $t = -7$, so the figure emphasizes relative pre-payment movements rather than level differences. The green shaded interval marks an earlier diagnostic window from $t = -12$ to $t = -7$, while the blue shaded interval corresponds to the reporting and anticipation phase leading into the first payment date. This design permits a direct visual assessment of whether treated and matched-control prices move similarly before the policy becomes financially binding.

The figure suggests that support for the parallel-trends assumption is uneven across categories. For some groups, such as To-go cups and Food containers, treated and matched-control series move reasonably closely over parts of the pre-payment window, although short-run deviations remain. For other categories, however, divergence is already visible before payment onset. Balloons and Plastic wrap show substantial downward movement in the treated series

relative to the matched control during the anticipation window, while Wet wipes and Non-deposit bottles display pronounced instability in the matched comparison itself. Deposit bottles and Plastic bags also exhibit noticeable pre-period volatility, which limits confidence in strict trend comparability. Tobacco filters show somewhat closer co-movement earlier in the window, but this pattern weakens as treatment approaches.

Taken together, Figure D6 does not provide uniform support for a common-trends assumption across all treated categories. Instead, it indicates that pre-treatment fit varies materially by product group, implying that category-specific estimates should be interpreted with differing degrees of caution. In particular, categories with visibly diverging pre-trends are more exposed to confounding from category-specific demand shifts, input-cost movements, or composition changes that predate the payment phase. For this reason, the category-level results in the main text are best interpreted as evidence on heterogeneous pricing responses rather than as equally persuasive causal estimates for every treated subgroup.

Per-Category Parallel-Trend Check: Treated vs. Matched Control
 (Green zone: $t-12$ to $t-7$ check window; Blue zone: reporting/anticipation)

Figure D6: Per-category parallel-trends check comparing treated and matched-control price indices before payment onset. Each panel indexes the treated and matched-control series to 100 at $t = -7$, where $t = 0$ corresponds to March 2024. The green shaded region marks the earlier diagnostic window from $t = -12$ to $t = -7$, and the blue shaded region marks the reporting and anticipation phase. Pre-treatment trend similarity varies substantially across categories.

D.4 Regression coefficient plots for the original non-aggregated offer-spell data

This subsection reports coefficient plots corresponding to the regression results for the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. The figures complement the regression tables in the main text and appendix by displaying the magnitude, precision, and heterogeneity of the estimated treatment effects under the principal fixed-effects specifications.

Figure D7 summarizes the pooled treatment effects from the baseline two-way fixed-effects specifications. The left panel reports the standard TWFE estimate with a single post-payment interaction, while the right panel reports the sequential 3×2 specification that distinguishes the reporting-only phase from the payment-due phase. The pooled post-payment estimate is positive but modest in magnitude, whereas the sequential specification shows more clearly that the larger adjustment already occurs during the reporting phase. This pattern is consistent with anticipatory price adjustment before the first fully binding payment date, rather than a discrete repricing only after fees became due.

Figure D7: Coefficient plots for the pooled TWFE specifications using the original non-aggregated offer-spell sample. The left panel reports the standard TWFE estimate with a single post-payment interaction. The right panel reports the sequential 3×2 TWFE specification separating the reporting-only and payment-due phases. Points show coefficient estimates and horizontal bars indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Figure D8 reports category-specific TWFE coefficients ordered by expected SUP exposure. The figure shows clearly that the pooled average masks substantial heterogeneity across product classes. Tobacco filters and Food containers display positive and comparatively precise estimates, while Wet wipes, Plastic wrap, and Non-deposit bottles show negative coefficients. To-go cups, despite being the largest treated category in the sample, exhibit only a small negative estimate. Plastic bags stand out with a very large positive point estimate but also extremely wide confidence intervals, indicating that inference for this thin category is imprecise. Overall,

the category plot supports the interpretation that regulatory exposure and pass-through differ sharply across treated product groups.

Figure D8: Category-specific TWFE estimates for the original non-aggregated offer-spell sample, ordered by expected SUP exposure. Points show category-level treatment coefficients in log points and horizontal bars indicate 95% confidence intervals.

D.5 Regression coefficient plots for aggregated duration-weighted offer-spells on the balloons subsample

Figure D9 focuses on balloons as a high-exposure case study. The corresponding event-study coefficients indicate a large and immediate increase around the first payment date, with effects remaining elevated for several months before attenuating toward the end of the sample window. This figure shows particularly clearly how pooled estimates compress substantial within-treated heterogeneity. For balloons, the estimated post-payment response is not only positive but also economically large, which is consistent with stronger pass-through in narrowly defined categories with direct and transparent exposure to the Austrian SUP regime.

Figure D9: Event-study coefficients for Austrian balloon prices in the original non-aggregated offer-spell data. Points show month-specific coefficient estimates relative to the omitted pre-payment reference period, and vertical bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. The vertical dashed line marks the first payment month.

Taken together, these coefficient plots reinforce the main regression findings of the paper. The pooled TWFE estimates point to a positive average pricing response, but the sequential specification shows that a substantial part of the adjustment already occurs during the reporting phase. The category-specific estimates further show that the average effect conceals strong heterogeneity across product groups, and the balloon event study highlights that highly exposed categories can experience much larger and more persistent price increases than the pooled estimates suggest.

D.6 Energy input-price series: full sample and event window

This subsection documents the three energy input-price series used as supplementary controls in the extended specifications. Figure D10 presents all three series in a 2×3 grid: the top row covers the full sample from January 2020 to December 2025, and the bottom row restricts attention to the estimation event window from March 2023 to March 2025, which brackets treatment onset by twelve months on either side. The vertical dotted line marks the onset of the reporting phase in March 2023, and the vertical dashed line marks the onset of the payment phase in March 2024. Blue shading indicates the reporting-only period and red shading the payment-due period.

Figure D10: Energy input-price controls: full sample (top row) and event window (bottom row). Left column: Brent crude oil (USD/bbl, FRED). Centre column: German energy import price index (2021=100, Destatis). Right column: Austrian natural gas spot price (€/MWh, OEGPI). Vertical dotted line: reporting-phase onset, March 2023. Vertical dashed line: payment-phase onset, March 2024. Blue shading: reporting-only period. Red shading: payment-due period.

Several features of these series are relevant for the identification discussion in Section 5. All three indicators peak sharply in 2022, reflecting the European energy crisis following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. The German energy import index reaches its maximum

in August 2022 at roughly 260 with 2021 as the base year, and Austrian gas prices peak in September 2022 at about €216 per MWh. Brent crude reaches roughly \$122 per barrel in June 2022. By the onset of the reporting phase in March 2023, all three series had declined substantially but remained materially above their pre-2022 levels: Brent was still around \$78 per barrel, the German index around 135, and Austrian gas around €55 per MWh. These elevated levels during the reporting-only phase are relevant for identification because lagged energy costs accumulated during the 2022 spike could still have been passing through plastics and packaging supply chains during the reporting phase, raising input costs for treated products independently of the SUP compliance obligation.

By payment onset in March 2024, energy prices had declined further toward more moderate levels: Brent was around \$85 per barrel, the German import index around 114, and Austrian gas around €27 per MWh. The event window in the bottom row of Figure D10 makes this decline clear and also shows that the three series continued to ease through the remainder of 2024 before Austrian gas prices began to firm again in late 2024 and early 2025. This declining energy-price environment during the post-payment window is, if anything, favorable for identification: falling input costs should have exerted downward pressure on treated prices during this period, so the positive post-treatment coefficients in the main results are unlikely to be driven by a concurrent energy-cost shock. The more serious concern runs in the other direction: elevated lagged energy costs during the reporting phase could inflate the reporting-period coefficient. That concern is discussed in the identification-threats subsection of the empirical results.

Figure D11 presents the three series over the event window alone at a larger scale for ease of inspection, with end-of-window values annotated. Figure D12 presents the full sample in the same three-panel format for completeness.

Energy Input-Price Controls: Event Window (Mar 2023 – Mar 2025)

Figure D11: Energy input-price controls, event window only (March 2023 to March 2025). Panels show Brent crude (left), German energy import index (centre), and Austrian gas price (right). Annotated values indicate the end-of-window observation. Shading and vertical lines follow Figure D10.

Energy Input-Price Controls: Full Sample

Figure D12: Energy input-price controls, full sample (January 2020 to December 2025). Panels show Brent crude (left), German energy import index (centre), and Austrian gas price (right). Shading and vertical lines follow Figure D10. The 2022 price spike motivates the inclusion of lagged energy controls in extended specifications.

Appendix E: Alternative Duration-Weighted Monthly Panel

This appendix documents the construction of the duration-weighted unit-month panel used in all empirical results. The starting point is two spell-level source files: *plastics_regulation_obs.csv*, which contains treated SUP-matched products, and *plastics_regulation_counterfactual_obs.csv*, which contains the graphics-card control sample. Section E.1 describes the variables in the raw files and in the derived panel *unit_month_weighted_prices.csv*. Section E.2 records the transformation from raw spells to unit-month observations. Section E.3 discusses sample construction. Section E.4 reports the appendix figures with full captions.

E.1 Data Dictionary

E.1.1 Raw Offer-Spell Schema (spell-level input files)

The two source files share a common schema. Each row corresponds to one *offer spell*, defined as a continuous interval during which a given retailer lists a given product. Table A7 lists the variables retained after cleaning.

Table A7: Raw spell-level data dictionary

Column name	Type	Description
sample_flag	string	Group label: <i>treated</i> (SUP products) or <i>control</i> (graphics cards).
angebot_id	integer	Unique offer-listing identifier.
produkt_id	integer	Numeric product identifier, mapping to a single EAN or article.
haendler_bez	string	Retailer slug (for example, <i>amazon-at</i>). This variable provides the retailer dimension of the unit identifier.
kunden_id	integer	Internal customer or contract identifier.
dtimebegin	integer ^a	Epoch-second start of the primary time bracket.
dtimeend	integer ^a	Epoch-second end of the primary time bracket.
dtimebegin_1	integer ^a	Epoch-second start of the offer spell; preferred start timestamp.
dtimeend_1	integer ^a	Epoch-second end of the offer spell; preferred end timestamp.

(continued from previous page)

Column name	Type	Description
dtype_birth	integer ^a	Epoch-second at first observation of the unit-listing; used as fallback spell start if dtypebegin_1 is missing.
dtype_death	integer ^a	Epoch-second at last observation of the unit-listing; used as fallback spell end if dtypeend_1 is missing.
preis_avg	numeric	Mean listed price in euro over the spell window. This is the main price measure used in the paper.
preis_min	numeric	Minimum listed price in euro over the spell.
preis_max	numeric	Maximum listed price in euro over the spell.
produkt_bez	string	Product description used for keyword-based SUP category assignment.
subsubkat	string	Sub-subcategory code from the platform taxonomy.
is_at	binary ^b	Equals 1 if the offer is listed on the Austrian domain. All analysis restricts attention to $is_at = 1$.
is_de	binary ^b	Equals 1 if the offer is listed on the German domain.
liefert_at	binary ^b	Equals 1 if the retailer ships to Austria.
laden	binary ^b	Equals 1 if the product is available for in-store pickup.
online	binary ^b	Equals 1 if the listing is online-only.
avail	integer	Platform-specific availability code.
anz_angebote	integer	Number of competing offers at listing time.
clicks_ijt	numeric	Click-through count for unit i at retailer j in week t .
lon	numeric	Retailer longitude in decimal degrees.
lat	numeric	Retailer latitude in decimal degrees.

(continued from previous page)

Column name	Type	Description
unit_id	string ^c	Composite unit identifier formed as produkt_id_haendler_bez, one identifier for each retailer–product pair.
spell_start	Date ^c	Calendar date of spell start, converted from dtimebegin_1 with fallback to dtime_birth.
spell_end	Date ^c	Calendar date of spell end, converted from dtimeend_1 with fallback to dtime_death; if still missing, set equal to spell_start.
dur_days	integer ^c	Total spell duration in calendar days, defined as $\max(1, \text{spell_end} - \text{spell_start} + 1)$.
treated	binary ^c	Equals 1 if and only if sample_flag is <i>treated</i> .
phase	factor ^c	Policy phase: <i>pre</i> (before 2023-03-01), <i>reporting_only</i> (2023-03-01 to 2024-02-28), or <i>payment_due</i> (on or after 2024-03-01).
rel_months	integer ^c	Months relative to payment onset, with 2024-03-01 defined as month 0.
baseline_survivor	binary ^c	Equals 1 if dtime_birth \leq 2020-01-01, indicating that the unit predates the estimation window.

E.1.2 Derived Unit-Month Panel (unit_month_weighted_prices.csv)

After aggregation, the unit-month panel contains one row for each unit–month pair. The full panel contains 102,627 rows and spans 2012-09 to 2025-01. The estimation window contains 43,371 rows and spans 2021-09 to 2024-12. Table A8 lists the variables in the derived file.

Table A8: Derived unit-month panel data dictionary (*unit_month_weighted_prices.csv*)

Column name	Type	Description
sample_flag	string	<i>treated</i> or <i>control</i> ; see Table A7.
unit_id	string	Retailer–product identifier of the form produkt_id_haendler_bez. There are 3,219 unique units, of which 2,580 are treated and 639 are controls.

(continued)

Column name	Type	Description
product_id	integer	Numeric product identifier; 675 unique products.
retailer_id	string	Retailer slug; 314 unique retailers.
month_date	Date	First calendar day of the observation month.
price	numeric	Duration-weighted geometric mean price in euro for unit i in month t .
price_unweighted	numeric	Unweighted arithmetic mean of <code>preis.avg</code> across all spells for unit i in month t ; retained for specification checks.
total_days_covered	integer	Total number of spell-days with positive overlap in month t .
n_spells_in_month	integer	Number of distinct spells contributing to the unit-month observation.
dur_days	numeric	Mean total spell duration, in days, across spells contributing to the cell.
product_title	string	First non-empty product description carried over from <code>produkt.bez</code> .
treated	binary	Treatment indicator D_i , equal to 1 for treated units.
post_treat ^a	binary	Equals 1 if <code>month_date</code> is on or after the payment date as recorded in the CSV; the stored anchor differs from the one used in the paper.
post_legal ^a	binary	Equals 1 if <code>month_date</code> is on or after the legal-binding date used in the CSV construction.
rel_month ^a	integer	Months relative to the payment date under the CSV anchor, 2023-12-01. <i>This field is not used in the regressions; event time is rebuilt directly from <code>month_date</code>.</i>
rel_month_legal ^a	integer	Months relative to the legal-binding date under the CSV anchor.
calendar_month_f	string	Month label in YYYY-MM format.

(continued)

Column name	Type	Description
ln_price	numeric	Natural logarithm of price when price > 0, and 0 otherwise. This is the regression outcome throughout the paper.
cat_tabak	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the tobacco-filters category.
cat_becher	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the to-go-cups category.
cat_lebensmittelbehaelter	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the food-containers category.
cat_tueten_folien	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the plastic-wrap or small-bags category.
cat_flaschen_ohne_pfund	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the non-deposit-bottles category.
cat_flaschen_mit_pfund	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the deposit-bottles category.
cat_plastiktueten	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the plastic-bags category.
cat_feuchttuecher	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the wet-wipes category.
cat_luftballons	boolean	Equals 1 for units assigned to the balloons category.

^a Reconstructed in the analysis scripts from month.date using the treatment dates adopted in the paper. The stored values of post_treat and rel_month in the CSV use a different anchor date, 2023-12-01, and are therefore not used in estimation.

Table A9 reports the number of units and unit-month observations by treatment status and policy phase.

E.2 Pipeline: Step-by-Step Construction

E.2.1 Step 1: Ingestion and Austria Filter

The two source CSV files are read using `data.table::fread()`. Variables are coerced to the target types listed in Table A7. The combined data are then restricted to listings on the Austrian

Table A9: Sample composition: unit and observation counts by group and policy phase

Group	Units		Unit-month observations		
	Full panel	Estimation window	Pre-announce	Reporting	Payment-due
Treated (SUP)	2,580	2,053	—	—	—
Balloons	212	—	—	—	—
Tobacco filters	170	—	—	—	—
Wet wipes	131	—	—	—	—
To-go cups	1,903	—	—	—	—
Food containers	80	—	—	—	—
Plastic bags	4	—	—	—	—
Plastic wrap	69	—	—	—	—
Non-dep. bottles	8	—	—	—	—
Dep. bottles	3	—	—	—	—
Control (graphics cards)	639	500	—	—	—
Total	3,219	2,553	—	—	—
Full panel rows	102,627 (calendar range 2012-09 to 2025-01)				
Estimation window rows	43,371 (2021-09 to 2024-12)				

Notes: The estimation window restricts the sample to $t \in [-30, +9]$ relative to payment onset on 2024-03-01. Category counts are mutually exclusive and follow the first-match rule, with the €450-per-tonne categories evaluated before the €225-per-tonne categories. Phase boundaries are defined as follows: pre-announce, before 2022-03-01; reporting, 2022-03-01 to 2023-02-28; payment-due, from 2024-03-01 onward.

domain, so that row r is retained if and only if $\text{is.at}_r = 1$. Rows with missing values of is.at are treated as zero and removed. No non-Austrian observations enter subsequent processing.²

E.2.2 Step 2: Timestamp Resolution and Spell Dates

Each row records the temporal span of an offer spell in Unix epoch seconds. The preferred timestamp pair is $(\text{dtimebegin}_1, \text{dtimeend}_1)$. The fallback pair $(\text{dtime_birth}, \text{dtime_death})$ is used when one or both preferred fields are missing. Spell start is defined as dtimebegin_1 when observed and dtime_birth otherwise. Spell end is defined as dtimeend_1 when observed, dtime_death when dtimeend_1 is missing and dtime_death is observed, and spell start otherwise. The resolved timestamps are converted from epoch seconds to UTC *POSIXct* values and then to calendar dates, yielding spell start s_r and spell end e_r . If $e_r < s_r$ after conversion, the end date is reset to the start date. Rows for which the spell start remains missing after all fallback steps are removed.

Spell duration in calendar days is defined as $\text{dur_days}_r = \max(1, e_r - s_r + 1)$.

E.2.3 Step 3: Unit Identifier

The unit of observation is the retailer–product pair. For row r , unit i is given by the pair $(\text{produkt_id}_r, \text{haendler_bez}_r)$, and the composite identifier is formed by concatenating pro-

²The Austrian-domain restriction is the principal geographic filter. Retailers that ship to Austria but appear on another domain, such as *.de*, are excluded.

dukt_id, a double underscore, and haendler_bez. A product sold by two retailers therefore defines two distinct units. Multiple offer spells for the same retailer and product remain attached to the same unit.

E.2.4 Step 4: Month Expansion

Each spell r covers a continuous interval $[s_r, e_r]$ that may cross month boundaries. The pipeline expands every spell into one record for each calendar month it overlaps. A month m belongs to the set of covered months for spell r if the first day of m is weakly earlier than e_r and the last day of m is weakly later than s_r .

E.2.5 Step 5: Days of Overlap

For each spell–month pair generated in Step 4, the number of active spell-days in month m is $d_{r,m} = \max(0, \min(e_r, m_{\text{end}}) - \max(s_r, m_{\text{start}}) + 1)$. Pairs with zero overlap are dropped.

E.2.6 Step 6: Duration-Weighted Aggregation to the Unit-Month Panel

Let \mathcal{S}_{it} denote the set of spells for unit i that are active in month t . The duration-weighted price is the geometric mean of spell-level prices using spell-days within the month as weights. Specifically, price for unit i in month t is $\exp(\sum_{r \in \mathcal{S}_{it}} d_{r,t} \ln p_r / \sum_{r \in \mathcal{S}_{it}} d_{r,t})$, where p_r denotes the spell-level mean listed price `preis_avg`. The panel also stores the unweighted arithmetic mean of spell-level prices for the same unit-month cell as a specification check. Total active spell-days in cell (i, t) equal $\sum_{r \in \mathcal{S}_{it}} d_{r,t}$ and are recorded as `total_days_covered`. The regression outcome is the natural logarithm of the duration-weighted price and is stored as `ln_price`.

E.2.7 Step 7: Treatment Indicators and Event Time

After aggregation, the pipeline appends treatment timing variables. Payment onset is fixed at 2024-03-01. Event time τ_{it} is measured as the signed month distance between month t and March 2024, so that negative values denote pre-payment months and $\tau = 0$ denotes the first payment month. The analysis scripts label this variable `rel_months`.

The sample period is partitioned into three mutually exclusive phases. The announcement phase runs from 2022-03-01 through 2023-02-28 and corresponds to $\tau \in [-24, -13]$. The reporting phase runs from 2023-03-01 through 2024-02-29 and corresponds to $\tau \in [-12, -1]$. The payment phase begins on 2024-03-01 and corresponds to $\tau \geq 0$. The pooled two-period specification uses a post indicator equal to one from 2022-03-01 onward.

The treatment indicator is $D_i = 1$ when `sample_flag` equals *treated* and 0 otherwise.

E.2.8 Step 8: SUP Category Assignment

Treated units are assigned to one of nine SUP categories using keyword matching on `produkt.bez`. The resulting category flags are appended as binary `cat_*` variables in both the spell-level and unit-month files. Assignment follows a first-match rule in the following order: Balloons, Tobacco filters, Wet wipes, To-go cups, Food containers, Plastic bags, Plastic wrap, Non-deposit bottles, and Deposit bottles. A treated unit is assigned to the first category whose keyword list matches a substring of the lower-cased product title. For control units, all category flags are set to FALSE.

The Austrian SUP regulation distinguishes two fee tiers. Balloons and Tobacco filters are subject to a fee of €450 per tonne of plastic placed on the market. The remaining seven categories are subject to a fee of €225 per tonne.

E.2.9 Step 9: Estimation Window and Regression Sample

The main estimation sample retains unit-month observations with $\tau_{it} \in [-30, +9]$, corresponding to 2021-09-01 through 2024-12-31. This window has three advantages. First, the pre-trend diagnostic interval, $\tau \in [-30, -25]$, lies entirely before treatment. Second, both the legislative announcement in 2022-03 and the reporting start in 2023-03 fall within the observed sample. Third, the panel includes nine post-payment months, $\tau = 0, \dots, 9$.

The pipeline constant `MAX_REG_N` places an upper bound on the number of rows used in regression estimation, with random seed 174, to limit run time when the expanded panel becomes large. In the present data, with 43,371 estimation rows, this cap does not bind.

E.3 Sample Construction in Detail

E.3.1 Treated Sample

The treated sample, identified by `sample_flag = treated`, is drawn from `plastics_regulation_obs.csv`, which contains all offer spells matched by the platform to at least one of the nine SUP keyword lists. After the Austrian restriction, timestamp resolution, and month expansion, the treated panel contains 2,580 distinct units over 149 calendar months. Within the estimation window, 2,053 treated units are observed.

The treated sample is heavily concentrated in To-go cups, with 1,903 units, or 73.8% of treated units. This concentration reflects both the breadth of the underlying keyword list and the high listing density of single-use beverage containers on the Austrian price-comparison platform. Balloons (212 units) and Tobacco filters (170 units) form the €450-tier subsample.

E.3.2 Control Sample

The control sample, identified by `sample_flag = control`, consists of baseline-survivor graphics-card listings, defined as units with `dtime.birth` on or before 2020-01-01. This restriction ensures that control units are observed on the platform before the estimation window begins. Graphics cards are used as controls for three reasons: they are sold online by many of the same retailers, they face the same broad macroeconomic cost environment, including energy prices, logistics costs, and electronics supply shocks, and they are unaffected by SUP regulation.

After the Austrian-domain restriction, the control panel contains 639 distinct units, of which 500 appear within the estimation window.

E.3.3 Identification of the Structural Break

In the present panel, each unit's duration-weighted price is constant across the months covered by a spell because spell-average prices are carried across overlapping months rather than measured as month-specific transaction prices. As a result, a standard two-way fixed-effects design with unit fixed effects absorbs essentially all within-unit variation in the price outcome and is therefore not informative for the treatment effect of interest.

The paper instead estimates a pooled OLS difference-in-differences specification with calendar-month fixed effects:

$$\ln p_{it} = \gamma_m + \sum_{k \in K} \beta_k (D_i \cdot \mathbf{1}\{k\}_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it},$$

where γ_m denotes a calendar-month fixed effect, partialled out by within-month demeaning, $K = \{\text{Post, Announce, Report, Payment}\}$, and ε_{it} is the disturbance term. Identification comes from changes in the cross-sectional price gap between treated and control units across policy thresholds. Standard errors are clustered at the retailer level. Retailer clustering is preferred to unit clustering because pricing decisions are likely to be correlated across products sold by the same retailer.

E.4 Figures

Figures [E13–E23](#) reproduce the appendix figures and provide full documentation of panel construction, estimation, and inference.

Figure E13: **Panel A (left): Spell-length distribution.** Histogram of the number of calendar months in which each unit is observed, shown separately for treated (navy) and control (crimson) units. The horizontal axis reports the number of months within the full panel, 2012-09 to 2025-01; the vertical axis reports kernel density based on 35 bins. A unit is counted in month m if at least one spell remains active after the month-expansion procedure in Step 4. **Panel B (right): Monthly observation counts.** Number of unit-month observations in the estimation window, 2021-09 to 2024-12, by treatment group and calendar month. Background shading denotes the policy periods: grey for the pre-trend diagnostic window ($\tau \in [-30, -25]$), yellow for the announcement phase ($\tau \in [-24, -13]$), blue for the reporting phase ($\tau \in [-12, -1]$), and red for the payment phase ($\tau \geq 0$). Vertical lines mark the three policy dates: long-dashed green for 2022-03-01, dotted blue for 2023-03-01, and dashed red for 2024-03-01. The decline in treated observations after 2024-03 reflects the end of available data for several treated categories.

Figure E14: **Panel A (left): Log-price distribution by treatment group.** Kernel density estimates of $\ln p_{it}$ for treated (navy) and control (crimson) units pooled across all months in the estimation window. The bandwidth is 0.20 under Silverman’s rule. The treated distribution is bimodal, reflecting heterogeneity across categories: To-go cups are concentrated at lower price levels, while balloons and tobacco filters occupy higher ranges. The control distribution, based on graphics cards, is unimodal with a long right tail driven by high-end listings. **Panel B (right): Log-price distribution by SUP category among treated units.** Separate kernel density estimates are plotted for each of the nine categories using bandwidth 0.25. Colours follow the exposure-ranked palette used throughout the appendix. The overlap between the To-go cups and Wet wipes distributions indicates similar price ranges, whereas balloons show higher and more dispersed prices, consistent with wider variation in product quality and pack size.

Figure E15: Horizontal bar chart of the number of treated units, defined by distinct `unit_id` values, in each of the nine SUP keyword categories. Categories are ordered from most to least common. Bar colours follow the exposure-ranked palette. Labels to the right of each bar indicate whether the category belongs to the €450-per-tonne or €225-per-tonne fee tier. To-go cups account for 1,903 units, or 73.8% of the treated sample, because the relevant keyword list captures a broad set of single-use beverage containers. Plastic bags, deposit bottles, and non-deposit bottles have at most eight units each, which sharply limits precision in category-specific estimates. Category assignment follows the first-match rule described above. Units that do not match any category keyword are excluded from category-specific analyses but remain in pooled treated-versus-control specifications.

Figure E16: **Panel A (left): Pooled price-index paths in the pre-payment period.** Mean log price is computed separately for treated and control units in each month and both series are normalised to 100 in February 2024, the last pre-payment month ($\tau = -1$). Background shading and vertical reference lines follow the conventions in Figure E13. Similar movement before treatment is required for the difference-in-differences interpretation. **Panel B (right): Pre-trend event-study coefficients.** The plot reports $\hat{\beta}_\tau$ for $\tau < 0$ from the pooled event-study specification, which interacts event-time indicators with D_i and omits $\tau = -1$. Calendar-month fixed effects are removed by within-month demeaning before OLS estimation. Standard errors are clustered at the retailer level. The dark ribbon indicates ± 1 standard error and the light ribbon the 95% confidence interval. The grey region, $\tau \in [-30, -25]$, is the designated pre-trend diagnostic window. Coefficients in this interval should be close to zero if the identifying assumption is tenable. The yellow region, $\tau \in [-24, -13]$, corresponds to the announcement phase, and the blue region, $\tau \in [-12, -1]$, to the reporting phase. Deviations from zero in these latter intervals are interpreted as anticipatory or reporting-phase price adjustment rather than as evidence against the design.

Per-Category Parallel-Trend Check
 (Grey: PT | Yellow: Announce | Blue: Report | Red: Pay)

Figure E17: Nine-panel display, one panel for each SUP category, showing the normalised price index for treated units in that category against the full control group. The treated series is shown as a coloured solid line and the control series as a dashed grey line. Both are normalised to 100 at $\tau = -25$ (2022-02), the final month of the designated pre-trend window. Background shading marks the grey pre-trend interval ($\tau \in [-30, -25]$), the yellow announcement phase ($\tau \in [-24, -13]$), and the blue reporting phase ($\tau \in [-12, -1]$). For each category, the identifying assumption requires treated and control series to move similarly during the grey interval. Divergence during the yellow or blue intervals is consistent with anticipatory repricing or reporting-phase adjustment and is therefore absorbed by the phase-specific interaction terms in the staggered specification. Categories with very small samples, notably Plastic bags and Deposit bottles, show volatile paths because they average over only a handful of treated units.

Figure E18: Forest plots of the main difference-in-differences coefficients. Thick horizontal bars denote $\pm 1\hat{\sigma}$ and thin lines denote the 95% confidence interval. Point estimates and significance markers are printed to the right of each estimate (** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$). All models are estimated by pooled OLS with calendar-month fixed effects, retailer-clustered standard errors, and the estimation window $\tau \in [-30, +9]$. **Panel A (left): Standard specification.** The model includes a single interaction, $D_i \cdot 1\{\tau_{it} \geq -24\}$, which captures the average post-announcement price differential between treated and control units. **Panel B (right): Three-period staggered specification.** The model includes separate interactions for the announcement, reporting, and payment phases. The payment-phase coefficient, approximately 0.39 with $p = 0.048$, is the main estimate of pass-through at the time the payment obligation takes effect.

Figure E19: Comparison of the three phase-specific difference-in-differences coefficients under two clustering schemes: retailer-level clustering, shown with circles and used in the main text, and unit-level clustering, shown with diamonds. Point estimates are unchanged across the two schemes; only estimated standard errors differ. Horizontal lines indicate 95% confidence intervals. The announcement and reporting coefficients remain statistically indistinguishable from zero under both clustering choices. The payment coefficient is significant at the 5% level under retailer clustering ($p = 0.048$) and remains below the 10% threshold under unit clustering. Unit-level clustering uses a larger number of clusters, 2,553 rather than 314, because units are nested within retailers.

Figure E20: Estimates of $\hat{\beta}_\tau$ for each event-time month $\tau \in [-30, +9]$ from the pooled event-study specification that includes the full set of interactions $D_i \cdot \mathbf{1}\{\tau_{it} = \tau\}$ and omits $\tau = -1$ as the reference month. Calendar-month fixed effects are removed before OLS estimation and standard errors are clustered at the retailer level. The dark ribbon shows $\pm 1\hat{\sigma}$ and the light ribbon the 95% confidence interval. The dashed horizontal line marks zero and the dashed vertical line marks the omitted month, $\tau = -1$. The grey region ($\tau \in [-30, -25]$) is the pre-trend diagnostic interval. The yellow region ($\tau \in [-24, -13]$) corresponds to the announcement phase. The blue region ($\tau \in [-12, -1]$) corresponds to the reporting phase. The red region ($\tau \geq 0$) corresponds to the payment phase. The rise in coefficients beginning around $\tau \approx -6$ (September 2023), followed by a persistently positive level from $\tau = 0$ onward, suggests repricing during the reporting phase that remained in place once payment became due.

Figure E21: Event-study coefficients for the Balloon category, estimated on the sample consisting of balloon-treated units and the full control group. The specification includes $D_i \cdot \mathbf{1}\{\tau_{it} = \tau\}$ interactions and omits $\tau = -1$. All plotting conventions match Figure E20. Annotations above the post-payment coefficients report Kennedy-corrected percentage effects, which adjust for retransformation bias in the log-linear model. Balloons fall under the €450-per-tonne fee tier and have no close reusable substitute on the platform, making this category the clearest setting in which to observe pass-through. The estimated effect in the first payment month, roughly 46 log points (about 58% after Kennedy correction), is consistent with nearly complete or even over-shifted pass-through relative to the mean wholesale price. Positive and rising coefficients during the pre-payment period indicate that price adjustment may have begun several months before the first payment date.

Figure E22: Forest plot of the category-specific post coefficient $\hat{\beta}_c^{\text{post}}$ from nine separate pooled OLS regressions, one for each SUP category. Each regression uses the treated units in category c together with the full control group and includes the single interaction $D_i \cdot \mathbf{1}\{\tau_{it} \geq -24\}$. Thick bars denote $\pm 1\hat{\sigma}$ and thin lines denote the 95% confidence interval. Point estimates and significance markers are printed to the right of each estimate. Categories are ordered by expected regulatory exposure, with the €450-per-tonne categories above the dashed divider and the €225-per-tonne categories below it. Within each fee tier, categories are ordered by the point estimate. Food containers produces the largest coefficient (approximately 0.71***), followed by Balloons (approximately 0.46**) and Tobacco filters (approximately 0.35***). Plastic wrap and Wet wipes display negative but statistically insignificant estimates, which is consistent with substitution toward cheaper alternatives or discounting during the regulatory run-up.

Figure E23: Forest plot of the payment-month event-study coefficient $\hat{\beta}_{\tau=0,c}$ for each SUP category. Estimates come from the category-specific event-study specifications using the same pooled OLS estimator and retailer-level clustering as in the main analysis. The coefficient $\hat{\beta}_{\tau=0,c}$ measures the log-price gap between treated and control units in March 2024, the first payment month, relative to February 2024, the omitted month with $\tau = -1$. Ordering, fee-tier divider, colour scheme, and confidence-interval conventions match Figure E22. The payment-month effects are generally larger in absolute value than the pooled post-announcement coefficients in Figure E22, which is consistent with partial repricing before 2024-03 followed by a renewed increase at the time the payment obligation takes effect. Plastic bags and Deposit bottles are omitted because the number of treated units in these categories is too small to support category-specific event-study estimation.